

Informed Consent Form

You are invited to participate in an online survey on Research Integrity and Research Fairness. The objective of this study is to provide evidence on the extent to which global health researchers adhere to principles of research fairness and research integrity. This research builds upon the BRIDGE guidelines for good epidemiological practice. This study is conducted by researchers from KIT Royal Tropical Institute (Netherlands) and KEM Hospital Research Centre (India) in collaboration with the University of the Free State (South Africa). It should take approximately 15 minutes to complete.

Why were you selected to participate in this study?

You were selected to join this study because your institute belongs to an international research network. For this survey we are inviting 30 individuals per sampled institute, across 60 institutes. Survey participants were sampled by two-stage cluster sampling. In the first sampling stage we randomly selected institutes from the above mentioned networks. In the second stage we compiled a list of all researchers working in the selected research institutes by referring to publicly available websites. We then randomly selected researchers from these lists. You were selected from this list and that is why we are inviting you to participate in our online survey.

What type of questions will we ask?

We will ask questions relating to your individual behaviour in the research you conducted in the past three years. There will be questions regarding responsible/questionable research practices and fair/unfair research practices. You will be asked to provide answers on a Likert scale indicating the frequency with which you engaged in these practices (never, very rarely, rarely, occasionally, frequently, very frequently, always). The following definitions apply:

- Questionable research practices: are defined in the field of research integrity as 'misbehaviours' in the grey zone between fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism and responsible conduct of research that violate traditional values of the research enterprise and that may be detrimental to the research process. The term describes practices such as describing a hypothesis after finding significant results, selective publication of results, concealing of conflicts of interests etc.**
- Unfair research practices: derive from the field of research fairness and refer to practices where there is unfair treatment of research partners in the planning, execution and dissemination of the research. Of particular concern in global health are practices that prevent local actors from shaping the research agenda in their country and curb their ability to reap scientific rewards for their contributions. These include bypassing local expertise and expert knowledge, avoiding local ethical institutions, failing to develop in-country capacity etc.**

Participation, Benefits and Confidentiality

What are the benefits of participating this study?

The main benefit of participating in the survey is to be a part of an initiative that aims to understand and improve global health research practice. With this prevalence survey we aim to quantify the prevalence of wanted and un-wanted behaviour. With follow-up in-depth interviews we will investigate the root causes, and more specifically we will attempt to disentangle individual determinants (career progression), structural issues (related to research funding) and institutional issues (related to institutions norms and policies).

What are the risks of participating this study?

Some questions may make you feel uncomfortable because they may make you reflect on some practices that, with hindsight, you regret. There will be comment boxes available for you to provide context to those answers if needed. We will take those comments into account in our analyses. Also remember that your participation in this survey is voluntary. You may refuse to take part in the research or exit the survey any time without penalty.

How will you ensure the confidentiality of my responses?

Your survey answers will be sent to a link where data will be stored in a password protected electronic format. We will not collect direct identifiers such as your name, email address, or IP address. At the end of the survey we will ask a few indirect identifiers which would improve the quality of the statistical analyses we could perform (gender, discipline, years of experience, academic rank and position). You may also chose to skip these personal questions entirely. If you skip these questions, you data will be 100% anonymized. The data will be handled on KIT servers in line with GDPR regulations.

How can I get more information about this survey? Should you have any questions or concerns, do not hesitate to contact the survey team at gep@kit.nl.

By clicking “next”, you confirm that you are aware of the purpose and procedure of this survey

Section A: Introduction

In order to better understand and contextualize the challenges of global health research, we would like to ask you one question first about your position in relation to global health research.

1. Which of the following best describes you?

Note: The terms Global North and Global South are not objective classifications based on geographic position, but instead subjective classifications based on socio-economic, political, and historic relations. You may not have a definitive answer based on your country of origin or life circumstances, thus select the answer you deem most appropriate.

To provide guidance, you can find two sources below which give an indication of how Global South and Global North may be classified. The first one is a link to the World Bank Income Categorizations (sometimes used in parallel to the Global North and Global South categorizations). The second is a generic map based on the historic Brandt Line

<https://datatopics.worldbank.org/world-development-indicators/the-world-by-income-and-region.html>

- Researcher from the Global North
- Researcher from the Global South
- Prefer not to disclose
- Other (please specify)

Section B: Responsible research practices (Part 1/2)

Now we would like to ask you some questions about how you conducted research in the past 3 years

* 1. In the last three years, I did *not* disclose who funded my studies and all my relevant financial and non-financial interests in my publications *despite* having explicitly been asked to do so

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 2. In the last three years, I took steps to correct errors in my published work whenever I and/or peers provided valid reasons for such a correction

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 3. In the last three years, I gave *insufficient* attention to the data collection tools essential to perform my studies

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 4. In the last three years, I gave *insufficient* attention to the skills or expertise essential to perform my studies

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 5. In the last three years, I *insufficiently* supervised or mentored junior co-workers

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 6. In the last three years, where appropriate, I pilot-tested or field-tested my research instruments prior to the start of effective data collection

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 7. In the last three years, I chose *inadequate* research designs or used evidently *unsuitable* measurement instruments for my studies

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 8. In the last three years, I drew conclusions that were *not* sufficiently substantiated by my studies

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 9. In the last three years, I pre-registered my study protocols in line with open science practices

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 10. In the last three years, I kept *inadequate* notes of my research process in a project

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 11. In the last three years, I did *not* mention clearly important details of my study method in my publications

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 12. In the last three years, I managed my research data carefully by storing both the raw and processed versions for a period appropriate to my discipline and methodology used

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 13. In the last three years, my research was published under open access conditions

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 14. In the last three years, when making use of other people's text in my publications, I cited the source accurately in accordance with the standards of my discipline

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 15. In the last three years, I chose *not* to submit or resubmit valid negative studies for publication

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 16. In the last three years, I fully disclosed and made accessible on open science platforms the underlying data used in my research

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 17. In the last three years, I fully disclosed and made accessible on open science platforms my underlying programming code or syntaxes used in my research

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 18. In the last three years, I *insufficiently* mentioned study flaws in my publications

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 19. In the last three years, I *insufficiently* mentioned limitations in my publications

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 20. In the last three years, before releasing results of my research, I meticulously checked my work to avoid errors and biases

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

Section B: Fair research practices (Part 2/2)

* 1. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, I did *not* consult representatives of affected populations during the preparation stage of research

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 2. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, I did *not* consult end-users of research during the preparation stage of research

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 3. The research I have been involved in over the last three years, was *planned* in partnership with local researchers

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 4. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, detailed research protocols were *prepared in consultation* with all research partners

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 5. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, research instruments were locally adapted and culturally appropriate

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 6. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years there were clear study plans agreed upon by all study partners

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 7. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years there were clear *decision-making processes* agreed upon by all study partners

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 8. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, ethical approval (or a waiver) was obtained from all *institutions* involved for data collection and data use concerning human subjects

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 9. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, ethical approval (or a waiver) from all *countries* involved was obtained for data collection and data use concerning human subjects

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 10. The research I have been involved in over the last three years was not *executed* in partnership with local researchers

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 11. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, data collection staff was selected according to both technical and cultural criteria

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 12. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, data was *not* collected in a respectful and safe manner and in an environment which safeguarded the confidentiality of respondents

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 13. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years there were *no* clear and fair data ownership agreements

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 14. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, *affected populations or their representatives* were consulted to develop lay dissemination products other than scientific publications

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 15. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, *end-users* were consulted to develop lay dissemination products other than scientific publications

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 16. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, lay dissemination products other than scientific publications were developed specifically for *end-users* of research

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 17. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, lay dissemination products other than scientific publications were developed specifically for *affected populations or their representatives*

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 18. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, the allocation and ordering of authorships in my publications were fair and in line with the standards of my discipline

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 19. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years there were clear and fair publication agreements which gave all members of the team an opportunity for career advancement and scientific recognition

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

* 20. In the research I have been involved in over the last three years, whenever data was made openly accessible, strategies were put in place to encourage secondary analyses by local researchers

Never	Very Rarely	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently	Always	N/A	Prefer not to respond
<input type="radio"/>								

Reason not applicable (N/A) or other comments

Section C: Personal information

In this section we would like to ask some personal questions. This information will NOT be shared with anyone outside the research team. Answers to these would help improve the quality of the statistical analyses we are planning. They are not compulsory and you may skip them all and simply press 'next' at the bottom of this page if you prefer not to disclose this information.

1. Which region of the world is your institute based in? (World Bank Classification)

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> East Asia and Pacific | <input type="radio"/> North America |
| <input type="radio"/> Europe and Central Asia | <input type="radio"/> South Asia |
| <input type="radio"/> Latin America and Caribbean | <input type="radio"/> Sub-Saharan Africa |
| <input type="radio"/> Middle East and North Africa | <input type="radio"/> Prefer Not To Disclose |

2. What is the commonly used name of your institute? (Not Compulsory)

Secondly, in order to take into account known confounders of research integrity and fairness in our analyses, the following information would be useful:

3. What discipline of global health based describes you:

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Biostatistics/Epidemiology | <input type="radio"/> Political sciences/Health economics |
| <input type="radio"/> Biology/Medicine | <input type="radio"/> Mathematics/Computer science |
| <input type="radio"/> Sociology/Anthropology | <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to disclose |
| <input type="radio"/> Other (please specify) | |

4. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to disclose
- Other (please specify)

5. How many years of involvement in research do you have?

- Early Career (< 3 years post-education)
- Mid-career (3-10 years post-education)
- Established (>10 years post-education)
- Prefer not to disclose

6. What is your highest academic qualification or position?

- Bachelor or Master degree
- PhD degree
- Postdoc or Assistant Professor
- Associate Professor or Full Professor
- Prefer not to disclose
- Other (please specify)

7. How best do you describe your current role?

- Researcher
- Research manager (I manage one or more research projects)
- Leadership position (I have management responsibilities beyond/independently of individual research projects and I am responsible for the strategic development of the unit/department/institute that I manage)
- Prefer not to disclose
- Other (please specify)

Section D: Survey closure

We are planning some key information interviews (qualitative research) to better understand the individual, institutional and structural determinants of research integrity and research fairness.

1. Would you like to participate in a follow-up interview?

Yes

No

If yes, please send us an email at gep@kit.nl with the following text: I am willing to be contacted for a follow-up interview

Many thanks for participating in this survey! We are very grateful for your time and answers. We would really appreciate the opportunity to further engage with you on this important topic